

AN INTEGRATIVE APPROACH TO THE EDUCATION SYSTEM AS A BASIS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF COMPETENCIES

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Abstract At the current stage of the development of our society, where deep economic and social changes are taking place, finding ways and means to improve the quality of education for students remains one of the main urgent tasks of modern pedagogy.

Key words: integrative, information technologies, problem-based learning, situations, communicative, ability to work with information, self-development competence as a person, socially active citizenship competence, general cultural competences, mathematical literacy, aware of science and technology news
Competencies to be and to use.

Introduction: To effectively organize the educational process, the use of pedagogical and information technologies on an integrated, integrative basis is a requirement of today. For this, it is necessary to raise an intellectually mature generation that meets the requirements of scientific, spiritual, sustainable development and cares for the future of our republic in a modern developed society.

By implementing an integrative approach to the continuous education process, it aims to implement the following tasks:

- To teach students to creatively apply the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities in new unexpected situations in order to meet the social needs of our country for young people who are able to solve the problems of society, science, production and independent life of the individual in the future;
- Satisfy the needs of students to learn the basics of science, develop their interests, and develop personal qualities while learning the content of education by creating problem learning situations;

- Knowledge standardized with DTS by focusing students' educational activities on specific objects and teaching them to solve existing problems, to achieve acquisition of creative activity experiences by students along with the formation of skills and qualifications;

- Directing students to the profession by increasing their readiness for specific practical activities, to the field of science as a result of the development of creative activity experiences;

- It is possible to prepare students for an independent life by applying the scientific and theoretical knowledge acquired from the subjects in practice in concrete and processual problem situations.

The main essence of teaching based on an integrative approach is to develop the competences to use the knowledge, skills and abilities acquired by students in the educational process organized by subjects in their personal life, as well as in their professional and social activities in the future. is counted

It is necessary for students to engage in personal, social, economic and professional relationships in the future, to take their place in society, to solve the problems encountered in this process, and most importantly, to be competitive in their field and profession. should have basic and subject-related competencies.

It is known that, through the educational process, students acquire basic and science-related competencies, including communicative, informational skills, self-development competencies as individuals, socially active citizenship competencies, general cultural competencies, mathematical literacy, is charged with the task of being aware of science and technology news and developing competences for use.

An integrative approach to the educational process is a set of general principles that allow the organization of the educational process based on innovative technologies and the analysis of the results of the enrichment of the educational content in order to achieve the educational goals.

Among them, it is necessary to consider the following:

- To develop the ability of students to solve problems in various activities and areas of independent life based on acquired knowledge, skills and competencies,

their own life experiences, observations, personal conclusions, and to perform the activities required in problematic situations appropriately;

- To increase students' interests in the selection of educational content and to create methodological support, to expand their scientific worldview, to solve moral, ideological-political, educational-educational problems, in the didactically processed self, students' first to apply the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities in new unexpected situations, to pay attention to educational tasks that allow to draw scientific conclusions based on their own life experiences and observations;

- The main goal in the organization of the educational process is to form students' knowledge, skills, qualifications, as well as information processing, communication skills, mathematical literacy, and social activity. create conditions for them to acquire experience in solving educational problems independently;

- Evaluating the results of the educational process based on the results achieved at a certain stage of this process, i.e. the level of knowledge, skills and competences acquired by students, which are the basis of competence;

- In the competence approach - teaching goals are students' self-awareness, understanding of ways to achieve learning goals in the educational process, activation of students' learning activities, students' personality targeting priorities such as adaptation to society and independent life, socialization through self-development.

Competence is divided into levels according to the methods of content acquisition and importance in a person's life.

Competencies that prepare the ground for the general development of a student's personality are called basic competence, and competences that are formed only through the subject of study are called special competences.

The analysis of the literature showed that the competences of students are divided into three levels:

1. Basic competencies - the content of all subjects included in the curriculum and the competencies that are formed through the teaching process.

2. General (subject) competences - competences that are formed by making interdisciplinary connections in the teaching of social-humanitarian, natural-mathematical and applied subjects included in the curriculum.

3. Special competences are the competences that are formed on the basis of knowledge, skills and qualifications in the educational process.

The student's competence is the ability to use and apply in practice the knowledge, skills and abilities acquired by the students in solving practical and theoretical problems encountered in their daily life.

In order to develop the above-mentioned basic competencies in the students, the analysis of the content of the academic subject, all forms of teaching: lessons, extracurricular activities, excursions, and activities outside the group are carried out in a systematic and coherent manner. should plan to increase.

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